

Yoga Benefit: Wellbeing of Indian Working Women in Post-Forties

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Abstract:

Women passing through mid of life; balancing career struggles and family chores' can enhance their lifestyle and wellbeing through different Yoga Practices. It is well known that Indian family structures are mostly dependent on Mothers, they take cares of the whole family, gives birth to baby, rears them with care and diligence, simultaneously tackles the office affairs . To maintain the balance of life, Women gradually ignore her health and wellbeing. In Post forties human aging begins, her hemoglobin along with calcium level can deteriorates. For working women in their forties, incorporating yoga into their routine can be a holistic approach to maintaining physical health, managing stress, and enhancing overall wellbeing. Yoga, when combined with a balanced diet, can aid in weight management. It increases metabolism and helps burn calories, which becomes increasingly important as metabolism naturally slows down with age. Certain yoga practices, such as restorative yoga and specific breathing techniques, are believed to support hormonal balance. This can help alleviate symptoms of menopause and promote overall wellbeing.

Key Words: Yoga, Women-Health, Balancing Of Life, Post- Forties, Menopause

Introduction:

Yoga is a holistic practice originating from ancient India that combines physical postures (asanas), breathing exercises (pranayama), and meditation. It is designed to promote physical, mental, and spiritual well-being. The word "yoga" itself means union, referring to the union of mind, body, and spirit. There are several types of yoga,

including Hatha, Vinyasa, Ashtanga, Bikram, and more, each emphasizing different aspects of the practice such as flexibility, strength, or relaxation. Yoga has gained popularity worldwide for its numerous health benefits, including stress reduction, improved flexibility, and enhanced mindfulness. Yoga offers a myriad of benefits tailored to the unique physical, mental, and emotional needs of women at different stages of their lives. From alleviating menstrual discomfort to managing stress and enhancing overall well-being, yoga can be a transformative practice for women.

Key Benefits of Yoga for Women:

Yoga offers numerous benefits that address the unique physical, mental, and emotional needs of women. These benefits span across various life stages and help in managing specific health concerns. Yoga helps regulate hormonal fluctuations, which is beneficial during menstruation, pregnancy, postpartum, and menopause. Yoga can alleviate menstrual cramps, reduce PMS symptoms, and promote relaxation during the menstrual cycle. Prenatal yoga helps maintain flexibility, strengthen the pelvic floor, and prepare the body for childbirth. Postpartum yoga aids in recovery, improves mood, and strengthens the core. Yoga can help manage symptoms of menopause such as hot flashes, mood swings, and sleep disturbances. Cooling and calming poses are particularly useful. Regular yoga practice reduces stress, anxiety, and depression. Mindfulness and breathing exercises promote mental clarity and emotional stability. Yoga can indeed reduce risk factors for cardiovascular disease by lowering blood pressure, improving lipid profiles, and enhancing overall heart function. Here are some of the key benefits of yoga for women:

1. Maintaining Hormonal Balance:
2. Keeping healthy Menstrual Health:
3. Pregnancy and Postpartum health management
4. Menopause related issues
5. Maintaining Mental Health

6. Maintaining Bone Health
7. Flexibility and Balance
8. Cardiovascular Health
9. Weight Management

Women in middle age:

Women in their forties and beyond face various health challenges due to physiological changes, lifestyle factors, and aging. Yoga can be a great way for middle-aged women to stay healthy and fit for a number of reasons. Cardiovascular disease (CVD) becomes more prevalent as women age, particularly after menopause due to the decline in estrogen levels, which provides some protection against heart disease. Osteoporosis is another significant risk due to decreased bone density after menopause. This condition increases the risk of fractures, particularly in the hip, spine, and wrist. The risk of breast cancer increases with age. Women in their forties should begin regular screenings to detect early signs of breast cancer. Type 2 diabetes becomes more common with age, partly due to lifestyle factors and the body's reduced ability to process insulin effectively. Depression and anxiety are common mental health issues that can affect women in their forties.

Strength and Flexibility: Yoga postures help improve strength and flexibility, which are essential for maintaining mobility and preventing age-related decline. It suggests that even simple exercises can be beneficial for older women.

Bone Health: Weight-bearing yoga poses can help improve bone density, which is crucial for women at risk of osteoporosis. (Curl) talks about the benefits of maintaining an active lifestyle for bone health in aging women.

Stress Management: Yoga is well-known for its stress-reducing benefits. (Ross et al.) found a link between yoga practice and perceived health improvements,

particularly for conditions like depression. This is particularly important for women dealing with the stresses of midlife.

Mindfulness and Body Awareness: Yoga encourages mindfulness and body awareness, which can help women make healthier choices and listen to their bodies' needs. It highlights the importance of being present in the moment, a concept often emphasized in yoga practice.

Research suggests that the practice of yoga can have a significant positive impact on the physical and mental wellbeing of working women, particularly those in the post-forties age group (Curtis et al.). Yoga has been shown to improve nervous system regulation, physiological system functioning, and psychological well-being, all of which are important for managing the demands and stresses that working women face. The low-to-moderate activity level of yoga makes it an accessible and appropriate activity for this population.

Now according to expert advice, the most beneficial Yogic poses for women in middle aged are-

For Strength and Bone Health:

- **Warrior II:** Strengthens legs, improves balance. mentions a pose with a similar focus on leg strength and balance.
- **Triangle Pose:** Strengthens legs, core, and back, stretches hips and hamstrings.

Downward-Facing Dog or Adho Mukha Svanasana: Strengthens arms, shoulders, back, and legs, stretches hamstrings and calves.

For Flexibility and Balance:

- **Tree Pose or Tadasana:** Improves balance and coordination, strengthens legs and core.

- **Cat-Cow Pose or Marjaryasana-Bitilasana:** Improves spinal flexibility, stretches back and core.

Seated Forward Bend or Uttanasana: Stretches hamstrings, spine, and shoulders.

For Stress Relief and Relaxation:

- **Child's Pose or Balasana:** Calms the nervous system, relieves stress and anxiety.
- **Corpse Pose or Sabasana:** Promotes deep relaxation, reduces stress and tension.

Conclusion:

Incorporating yoga into the lifestyle of middle-aged women can offer a holistic approach to managing the physical and mental health challenges of aging. Regular practice can lead to improved flexibility, better cardiovascular health, enhanced mental well-being, and overall improved quality of life. For optimal benefits, it is recommended to practice yoga under the guidance of a qualified instructor, especially for those new to yoga or with existing health conditions.

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